

ELICIT: The AI Research Assistant

Elicit is an AI assistant for researchers and academics, incubated at Ought and now running as an independent public benefit corporation.

USERS

Elicit is designed for students, independent researchers, and researchers from academic and independent organization.

Beginners often face trouble while using Elicit. So, here is a guideline for them.

Step -1

This is the search interface. Here, one can ask any research query, and you will get related papers.

Step -2

After asking a query, at first you will get summary of top four papers.

The screenshot shows the Elicit web interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with 'Elicit', 'Notebooks', and 'Library' options. A search bar contains the query 'Information seeking behavior'. Below the search bar, a dropdown menu indicates 'Summary of top 4 papers'. A paragraph of text provides a summary of the search results, mentioning authors like Wilson (2000) and Mahajan (2009). At the bottom, there's a table with columns for 'Paper' and 'Abstract'. The first row shows a paper titled 'Information-Seeking Behavior: A Study of Panjab University, India'. A 'Manage Columns' panel is visible on the right side.

You can upgrade your plan to see summary of top eight papers.

This screenshot is similar to the previous one but shows an 'UPGRADE' button next to the 'Summary of top 8 papers' dropdown. The text summary below is partially obscured by the 'UPGRADE' button. The table at the bottom shows a paper titled 'Information Seeking Behavior of Research Scholars' with 12 citations and a DOI link. The 'UPGRADE' button is highlighted in a light blue color. The interface also shows a 'Sort: Most relevant' option and a 'Filters' button.

Step -3

Then, you will see many papers and their abstract summary.

The screenshot shows the Elicit search results page for the query 'Information Seeking Behavior'. The page displays a list of papers with their titles, authors, and abstract summaries. The first paper is 'Information-Seeking Behavior: A Study of Panjab University, India' by P. Mahajan, published in 2009 with 15 citations. The second paper is 'Understanding Information Seeking Behavior of Users in Academic Context (A Critical Review of Literature)' by Salik Parveaz, published in 2022 with 1 citation. The third paper is 'Human Information Behavior' by Thomas D. Wilson, published in 2000 with 1,452 citations. The fourth paper is 'Information behavior and seeking' by Peiling Wang, published in 2000 with 1,452 citations. The page also includes a 'Manage Columns' sidebar on the right, which allows users to search for or create columns to extract specific data from the results. The sidebar shows options like 'Summary', 'Main findings', 'Methodology', 'Intervention', 'Outcome measured', and 'Limitations'. The bottom of the screenshot shows the Windows taskbar with the date and time as 11:18 AM on 13-12-2024.

Step -4

By clicking on the PDF option, you will get the full text of the paper.

The screenshot shows the full text of the paper 'Human Information Behavior' by T.D. Wilson, published in the journal 'Informing Science' (Volume 3 No 2, 2000). The paper is part of a 'Special Issue on Information Science Research'. The abstract states: 'This paper provides a history and overview of the field of human information behavior, including recent advances in the field and multidisciplinary perspectives.' The keywords are 'human information behavior, information seeking, research, user studies.' The introduction discusses the evolution of information systems and the need for a better understanding of user behavior. The paper also includes a section on 'Some Definitions' and a definition of 'Information Behavior'. The bottom of the screenshot shows the Windows taskbar with the date and time as 11:28 AM on 13-12-2024.

Step -5

You can sort these papers by their categories.

The screenshot shows the Elicit interface with a list of papers. A dropdown menu is open, showing sorting options: Most relevant, Most recent, Least recent, Most cited, Least cited, and Title (alphabetical). The 'Least recent' option is selected. The interface also shows an 'Abstract summary' column and a 'Manage Columns' panel on the right.

Step -6

You can filter these papers by their publication year, journal quality.

The screenshot shows the Elicit interface with a list of papers. A filter panel is open, showing options for 'Has PDF', 'Publication year' (1976-2024), 'Journal quality' (Q1-Q4), 'Study Type' (Review, Meta-Analysis, Systematic Review, RCT, Longitudinal), and 'Abstract Keywords'. The 'Has PDF' filter is checked. The interface also shows an 'Abstract summary' column and a 'Manage Columns' panel on the right.

Step -7

Here, you will be able to add those keywords, you want to see in papers. And you can choose a word, which you don't want in papers.

The screenshot shows the Elicit search interface with a filter overlay. The filter overlay includes the following sections:

- Publication year:** A slider from 1976 to 2024.
- Journal quality:** A slider from Q1 to All.
- Study Type:** Checkboxes for Review, Meta-Analysis, Systematic Review, RCT, and Longitudinal.
- Abstract Keywords:**
 - Abstract contains: Search box with 'information', 'Add' button.
 - Abstract does not contain: Search box, 'Add' button.

The background shows a list of search results with abstract snippets. A '0 papers selected' indicator is visible at the bottom of the results area.

Step -8

You can add a new column from the 'Manage Columns' section.

The screenshot shows the Elicit search results table with a 'Manage Columns' sidebar open. The table has the following columns:

Paper	Abstract summary	Summary
<input type="checkbox"/> Information-Seeking Behavior: A Study of Panjab University, India P. Mahajan 2009 - 15 citations	The study examines the information-seeking behavior of undergraduates, postgraduates, and researchers at Panjab University in India.	This paper explores the information-seeking undergraduates, postgraduates, and research University in India, examining their academic needs, preferred resources, satisfaction with collections, and patterns of information-seeking.
<input type="checkbox"/> Understanding Information Seeking Behavior of Users in Academic Context (A Critical Review of Literature) Salik Parveaz +1 ECS Transactions 2022 - 1 citation DOI	The paper reviews the information seeking behavior of users, especially faculty and students, in academic settings, with the Internet being the most used source.	The paper reviews the literature on information behavior of users, particularly faculty and students in academic settings, focusing on information needs, factors, and challenges at information seeking, and the influence of these practices.
<input type="checkbox"/> Human Information Behavior Thomas D. Wilson Informing Sci. Int. J. an Emerg. Transdiscipl. 2000 - 1,452 citations PDF DOI	This paper defines and distinguishes between information searching behavior, information seeking behavior, and information use behavior.	The paper provides an overview of the field of information behavior, tracing its historical development and the shift from a system-centered to a person-centered approach.
<input type="checkbox"/> Information behavior and seeking	Information behavior describes the ways in which people	Not mentioned (there is no summary provided)

The 'Manage Columns' sidebar is open on the right, showing the following options:

- Search or create a column:** Search box with 'e.g. Limitations, Survival time'.
- CURRENT COLUMNS:** Summary.
- ADD COLUMNS:** Main findings, Methodology, Intervention, Outcome measured, Limitations, Intervention effects, Summary of introduction, Summary of discussion, Study design.

You can add columns one by one.

Step -9

Then you can add new steps to your query.

Step -10

In 'Notebooks' section, you will see your search histories.

Step -11

In 'Library' section, you can upload your papers and search for analysis.

Step - 12

By clicking the 'Help' menu, you will see Help Centre, Contact Us etc sub-menu.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `elicit.com/notebook/e548c02b-5ee5-4a64-be3a-234573902717`. The page title is "Information Seeking Behavior Analysis". A search bar contains the text "Information seeking behavior". Below the search bar, there is a "Summary of top 4 papers" section with a "Copy" button. The main content area displays a paragraph of text about information seeking behavior, mentioning authors like Wilson (2000) and Mahajan (2009). At the bottom of the page, there is a navigation bar with "Sort: Most relevant", "Filters", "Export as", "UPGRADE", and a checkmark with the number "16". A "Manage Columns" panel is visible on the right side of the page, showing "Search or create a column". The browser's address bar and the Windows taskbar are also visible.